

TOWARDS HOLISTIC EDUCATION: OPPORTUNITIES AND BARRIERS IN ADOPTING SAHAJA YOGA MEDITATION IN SCHOOLS

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Paper Received On: 20 JULY 2025

Peer Reviewed On: 24 AUGUST 2025

Published On: 01 SEPTEMBER 2025

Introduction

Globally, mental health challenges among adolescents have intensified, with data from the World Health Organization indicating that 10–20% of young individuals face psychological issues, many of which remain undiagnosed or untreated. (*Mental Health of Adolescents*, n.d.) India faces multiple extreme challenges in this domain, and the reason behind this is the huge adolescent population and minimal development, which is too ineffective in supporting mental health within the schools. (Patel et al., 2018) Resulting of these, most young individuals experience extreme levels of emotional imbalance, loneliness, feelings of being left out or ignored, belligerence, psychological drained and stress. In the findings of the UNICEF report (2021), India has approximately 253 million population of adolescents, and approximately over 50 million out of them are prone to seeking psychological assistance. (*The State of the World's Children 2021 | UNICEF*, n.d.) Instead of addressing the alarming needs, the educational system is unable to design and implement the appropriate interventions to address these concerns. Shri Mataji Nirmala Devi introduced Sahaja Yoga Meditation (SYM), which offers a distinctive approach to encourage mental well-being by assisting practitioners to attain a healthy and balanced state of mind. (Harrison et al., 1998)

SYM (Sahaja Yoga Meditation) differs from traditional meditation practices as it is an inclusive, non-religious approach and suitable for young people. It is different from traditional methods by not relying just on concentration or specific physical postures, instead emphasizing a state of thoughtless awareness or mental silence (Woodyard, 2011). This makes it more

accessible and appealing to a younger population who may find traditional practices too rigid or unfamiliar. Mental health in the Indian education system is often neglected and treated as a less important issue. It is highlighted and treated only when a problem arises related to this, instead of implementing preventive and cautious measures.

This paper presents a comprehensive Research-to-Practice (RTP) model that proposes SYM as a core mental health tool for Indian secondary schools. This model is derived from:

- Empirical field research conducted between 2022 and 2024 in Navi Mumbai.
- An extensive literature review of SYM's role in adolescent education.
- The SFRM (Solace for Ruffled Minds) framework for guided emotional learning.

This Research-to-Practice (RTP) framework aims to transform mental healthcare in the education system from a crisis-driven model to one that is preventive and included in the daily learning environment. With the inclusion of emotional regulation measures into routine classroom activities, the model fosters continuous support rather than solitary intervention. The wider vision is to include Sahaja Yoga Meditation (SYM) as a Nationwide Strategy for the mental well-being of youth, which also supports the goals of India's National Education Policy (NEP) 2020 and United Nations Sustainable Development Goal 3 (good health and well-being) and 4 (Quality Education)

Literature Review: The adolescence phase is broadly recognized as a stage of life where adolescents are more vulnerable to emotional turbulence, identity formation, and increased sensitivity to peer comparisons. In the Indian context, these typical developmental challenges are prone to get intensified by academic pressures, rigid education systems, and prevailing societal expectations. Such conditions continuously contribute to the struggle in mental health, including severe levels of anxiety, emotional dysregulation, and aggressive tendencies (Rentala et al., 2019). A significant 73% of adolescents in our country meet the criteria for psychological disorders, according to the National Mental Health Survey (2015-16). Many students also face non-clinical emotional or behavioural challenges that impact their well-being. Secondary school students are particularly at risk due to academic, social, and personal pressures, as highlighted by a meta-analysis by Balamurugan et al. This study found high levels of anxiety, depression, and digital addiction among Indian adolescents, often tied to poor stress management. Other research, including studies by Deb and Walsh (2012) and Ghosh and Deb (2015), shows a link between academic stress and emotional issues, often exacerbated by high parental pressure. Insufficient mental health resources in schools worsen the situation, as seen in a localized study in Delhi by Arora et al. (2020). Despite the need, efforts to integrate mental

health programs in schools are lacking. However, research highlights Sahaja Yoga Meditation (SYM) as beneficial, with Chourasia et al. (2024) reporting reduced anxiety and improved emotional maturity among students practicing SYM in Navi Mumbai. SYM also positively affects physiological responses, promoting calmness and mental clarity (Sahaja Online, n.d.).

Theoretical and conceptual framework: A solid conceptual base is essential for developing and evaluating mental health programs in schools. This research integrates ideas from modern psychological theories and ancient Indian philosophies to create a dual framework for incorporating Sahaja Yoga Meditation (SYM) in educational settings. Emotional Regulation Theory, proposed by Gross in 1998, underscores the need for managing emotions to enhance personal and social health. Schoolchildren encounter pressures such as academic challenges and peer influence, which, if unmanaged, can lead to emotional and behavioural issues. (Rathor et al., 2020) SYM aids mental health and emotional control by emphasizing mental wellness. Preliminary studies indicate that regular SYM practice improves students' emotional stability, stress handling, and resilience to negative thinking. (Sattarshetty, 2016) Moreover, this method draws from the Indian Knowledge System, incorporating spiritual and cultural practices that focus on mental and emotional health. Ancient texts like the Bhagavad Gita, Upanishads, and Patanjali's Yoga Sutras stress emotional balance, self-awareness, and detachment as vital mental qualities. SYM embraces these principles by activating inner energy (kundalini) to attain "thoughtless awareness," in line with the dhyana concept in yoga. (Rubia, 2009) The National Education Policy 2020 supports the holistic development of students, advocating practical learning methods that foster emotional and ethical growth inspired by Indian traditions. SYM fulfils these objectives by providing affordable and easily integrated well-being practices for regular school activities like morning assemblies. The Solace for Ruffled Minds (SFRM) framework, created by Ramashankar Chourasia and Geeta R. Thakur in 2022, includes SYM as part of emotional education. SYM enhances inner resilience, while SFRM offers external support through teacher-led activities and group discussions, ensuring its sustained application.

In short, this research consolidates four key pillars, viz.

Emotional Regulation Theory (Western Psychology)
Indian Knowledge System (IKS) - cultural and spiritual roots
NEP 2020's goals
SFRM framework (for involvement and engagement)

The above core components facilitate the foundation for the Research-to-Practice (RTP) model explored in this study

Objectives and Hypothesis: This study intends to explore how positively Sahaja Yoga Meditation (SYM) can influence the emotional and psychological well-being of students in the Indian education system. It aims to develop the Research-to-Practice (RTP) framework in a way that can enable the implementation of SYM in the school environment in a large-scale and sustainable manner.

a. Objectives of the study:

- To examine how SYM influence the emotional structure and conditions of secondary school adolescents
- To assess whether the practice of SYM leads to measurable declines in emotional and mental issues such as stress, aggression and social nervousness
- To gather quality-based feedback from adolescent students based on their experiences and inner changes during the SYM sessions.
- To integrate the SYM program within the “Solace for Ruffled Minds” (SFRM) framework, making it feasible for teachers to lead school-wide mental health initiatives.
- To design a policy-compatible RTP model that aligns with India's National Education Policy (NEP)2020 and contributes toward Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) 3 & 4.

b. Research Questions:

1. Does consistent engagement in SYM practice result in statistically significant growth in emotional maturity among students?
2. Can SYM interventions lead to a reduction in symptoms related to stress, aggression, and social discomfort among adolescents?
3. What are the internal, lived experiences of students who regularly engage with SYM?
4. In what ways can SYM be integrated into school systems using a structured RTP framework?

5. What are the possible opportunities and challenges in implementing SYM at a larger scale across Indian secondary schools?

c. Hypotheses:

Based on the research aims and previous studies, the following hypotheses were developed:

This study employed a mixed-methods approach to thoroughly assess the impact of Sahaja Yoga Meditation (SYM) on the mental and emotional well-being of adolescents in secondary schools. Quantity and quality-based methods collected both measurable and experiential insights. Quantitative techniques were used to track changes in key psychological indicators, whereas qualitative tools like students' feedback and reflective exercises provided a wider understanding of participants' experiences with Sahaja Yoga Meditation (SYM).

Research Design: The study adopted the quasi-experimental test designs. Students were divided into two groups: one which was fostered to engage in daily SYM practice for almost 8 weeks, while the other continued with their standard academic schedule without any interruption. To enrich the numerical data, quality-based inputs were gathered in a structured manner through interviews and written reflections.

Setting and Sample: The research was conducted for about two years (2022–2024) across three secondary schools of the Maharashtra State Board, Navi Mumbai.

About 120 students, aged between 13 and 17 years, participated in the study. They were equally divided into:

- Intervention Group: 60 students who regularly practiced SYM.
- Control Group: 60 students with no practice of SYM

A purposeful sampling technique was used to select schools that showed interest in implementing well-being initiatives. Among the selected schools, students were randomly assigned to either the intervention or control group to ensure that there would be balanced and proper representation of the same.

Intervention Details: Sahaja Yoga Meditation (SYM): The SYM intervention included daily 15-minute meditation sessions, mostly conducted during morning assemblies or value education sessions. These sessions were availed by either trained SYM practitioners or school teachers who had undergone orientation under the Solace for Ruffled Minds (SFRM) framework. The ultimate purpose was to provide a consistent and accessible introduction to meditation practices for the students.

Key components of the intervention included:

- Focusing on achieving a state of thoughtless awareness
- Noticing internal sensations and emotional responses
- Engaging in self-reflection following each session

Tools for Quantitative Data Collection: The following standardized psychological instruments were used to measure pre- and post-intervention changes:

- Liebowitz Social Anxiety Scale (LSAS): Evaluates levels of anxiety and avoidance in social settings.
- Buss–Perry Aggression Questionnaire (BPAQ): Measures physical and verbal aggression, anger, and hostility.
- DASS 42 Stress Scale: Assesses levels of stress in everyday life.
- Emotional Maturity Scale (EMS): Analyses emotional stability, impulse control, and interpersonal sensitivity.

All tools demonstrated strong reliability, with Cronbach's $\alpha > 0.70$.

Qualitative Data Collection:

- Student Journals: Participants kept weekly journals to document their emotional state before and after meditation.
- Semi-Structured Interviews: Conducted with 15 students from the intervention group after the program.
- Teacher Observations: Teachers maintained informal notes on behavioural changes and classroom conduct.

Data Analysis

- Quantitative Data: Paired sample t-tests were used to compare students' scores before and after the intervention. Results were considered statistically significant at $p < 0.05$.
- Qualitative Data: Thematic analysis was performed using NVivo software to identify key emotional and behavioural patterns reported by students.

Ethical Considerations

- Informed consent was obtained from students, their parents, and school principals.
- All participants were informed that involvement was voluntary.
- Confidentiality and anonymity were strictly maintained

Results (Quantitative & Qualitative): This section presents the outcomes of the SYM intervention through both quantitative measurements and qualitative reflections, offering a comprehensive view of its influence on students' emotional well-being.

a. Quantitative Findings: The analysis of pre- and post-intervention scores in the experimental group revealed noticeable and statistically significant improvements in various psychological indicators as mentioned below:

- Stress levels showed a considerable decrease after consistent SYM practice.
- Aggressive tendencies—both verbal and physical—declined sharply.
- Social anxiety scores dropped, indicating enhanced interpersonal comfort.
- Emotional maturity scores rose significantly, reflecting better emotional regulation and behavioural awareness.

Interpretation:

1. The intervention based on SYM had positive change among the adolescents. They consistently reported a decline in psychological stress and betterment in the overall status of mental well-being.

2. Key qualitative themes: Through written evidences and interviews three recurring themes were revealed from students who practiced Sahaja Yoga Meditation:

- Students experienced calmness internally and emotionally balanced expressing that they could now remain relieved under pressure also and combat the setbacks with patience.
- They felt improved focus compared to before as it helped them to improve their concentration power for academic education and exam related tensions.

- Lastly, students noticed enhanced self-awareness, self-confidence and improved social relationships with the understanding of the importance of family and other social relationships.

Together, these insights suggest that SYM not only supports and encourages practicing emotional regulatory techniques but also gives its contribution to school based mental well-being initiatives which is essentially helpful for adolescent demographics. Collectively, the findings suggest that SYM fosters holistic development in adolescents.

Teacher Observations: Teachers overseeing students during the intervention period noticed significant changes: students paid more attention during lectures, and there was a reduction in classroom conflicts and disciplinary issues. The classroom environment was described as calmer and more cooperative. One teacher noted that students who were previously distracted and impulsive were now calmer and more respectful in class. These observations suggest that the SYM intervention not only improved psychological assessments but also led to positive changes in classroom behaviour and student attitudes.

Discussion: The outcomes of this study highlight the practical utility and cultural appropriateness of Sahaja Yoga Meditation (SYM) as a low-cost, scalable intervention to support adolescent mental health within Indian secondary education. The combined strength of measurable psychological improvements and qualitative student feedback offers a rich understanding of SYM's influence. (Hotkar, 2017) The reductions observed in students' stress levels, aggressive behaviours, and social anxiety are in line with earlier findings, such as those by Chourasia et al. (2024), who recorded a 23% drop in anxiety and emotional instability among students regularly practicing SYM. (Khyat et al., n.d.) This study not only confirms those results but extends them by using multiple psychometric instruments across three different school settings. The over 60% enhancement in emotional maturity found in this study is particularly noteworthy. It supports Gross's Emotional Regulation Theory (1998), which posits that consistent mindfulness practices enable individuals to regulate their responses to emotional stimuli, shifting from impulsive reactions to thoughtful responses.

Student Perspectives as Indicators of Inner Growth: An analysis of students' reflections shows a notable transition from emotional highs and lows to inner peace and mindfulness. Phrases like "I feel peaceful," "I no longer cry when upset," and "It feels like I'm floating" indicate that SYM fosters both behavioural stability and a more positive emotional self-view. These findings support the Indian Knowledge System (IKS) concept of atman-jnana, or self-realization, as crucial for personal growth. (Indian Knowledge Systems, n.d.) Teachers also

observed positive trends, such as enhanced concentration, peer collaboration, and emotional stability, creating a more harmonious learning environment. These developments are consistent with the Solace for Ruffled Minds (SFRM) framework, which promotes combining internal practices like SYM with structured support from educators. The research thereby supports a dual-delivery approach:

- Internal cultivation through daily SYM practice
- External guidance via teacher-led SFRM strategies and reflective writing exercises

One of the most compelling aspects of SYM is its universal accessibility. There are many other interventions which require costly medical professionals or institutional infrastructure but SYM is known to be:

- Free of cost and non-commercial
- Easy to learn and practice
- User-friendly to students as well as teachers
- Secular and inclusive of all belief systems.

The simplicity and ability to change make SYM especially valuable for supply-limited educational settings across both rural and city-based landscapes. In doing so, SYM advances the threefold mission of NEP 2020 - helping the development of thinking-related growth, emotional intelligence, and inner cognizance. The results strongly support the amalgamation of SYM into India's mainstream education policy.

Challenges and Opportunities: Although incorporating Sahaja Yoga Deep thinking (SYM) into India's secondary group of schools/teaching presents many advantages, its wide adoption depends on overcoming many practical, cultural, and institutional hindrances. At the same time, multiple ground-level and policy-driven enablers exist that support its wider putting into use.

Challenges:

- **Misunderstandings and Bias:** Despite SYM's objective and evidence-based approach, some stakeholders, particularly school administrators and parents, mistakenly link it with religious beliefs. This can create confusion, especially in culturally diverse educational settings.
- **Lack of Teacher Preparation:** Effective SYM sessions require well-prepared facilitators. Without structured training programs for teachers, schools might struggle to conduct these sessions efficiently.

- **Monitoring and Assessment Gaps:** Many schools lack the tools, metrics, or trained staff needed to track students' emotional development, complicating the assessment of SYM's long-term impact and consistency in implementation.
- **Academic Time Constraints:** Schools with strict schedules may hesitate to allocate even 10–15 minutes regularly to activities like meditation unless mandated by educational authorities.

Opportunities: The National Education Policy (NEP) 2020 strongly supports socio-emotional learning (SEL), character education, and essential life skills, areas where SYM aligns naturally. (*National Education Policy 2020 Ministry of Human Resource Development Government of India*, n.d.) NEP 2020's emphasis on these aspects allows for a seamless integration of SYM into the educational framework as follows: Early morning school prayer sessions, Ethics or moral classes, Life skills education and rejuvenation days, culturally acquainted and cost effective. Moreover, its no-cost implementation model makes it especially advantageous for government-run and financially constrained schools. (*NCERT*, n.d.)

Integration with Existing School Programs: SYM aligns well with ongoing national initiatives like: Fit India Movement, School Health and Wellness Programme (SHWP), CBSE's Value Education curriculum

Scalability through RTP and SFRM Models: Integrating the RTP model with the SFRM framework enables schools to implement SYM on their own, empowering teachers to lead and ensuring long-term success. By addressing challenges and utilizing support, SYM can evolve from a pilot to a scalable mental wellness solution in schools nationwide.

Policy Implications: The encouraging results of this research offer strong justification for integrating Sahaja Yoga Meditation (SYM) into the broader framework of Indian secondary education. This section outlines how SYM aligns with national policy priorities and suggests practical avenues for institutional integration.

Alignment with National Education Policy (NEP) 2020: The NEP 2020 articulates a forward-thinking educational philosophy centred on:

- Comprehensive personal development
- Emotional and spiritual growth
- Experiential and values-based learning
- Reviving and embedding Indian Knowledge Systems (IKS)

SYM naturally complements these priorities by providing:

- A hands-on meditative practice that fosters experiential learning

- Tools for developing self-awareness and emotional regulation
- A framework for nurturing ethical conduct and emotional intelligence
- A meaningful supplement to value education and life skills curricula

Excerpt from NEP 2020: “Education must develop not only cognitive capacities but also social, ethical, and emotional capacities and dispositions.” SYM strongly reflects this ideal by offering a structured yet flexible model for nurturing well-rounded students.

Advancing Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs): SYM also reinforces India’s dedication to the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals, especially **SDG 3: Good Health and Well-Being** and **SDG 4: Quality Education**

Potential for Integration into Current Educational Schemes: SYM can be smoothly embedded into existing national programs such as: NCERT’s Health and Physical Education curriculum, CBSE’s Life Skills modules, Samagra Shiksha Abhiyan’s mental health initiatives, Rashtriya Bal Swasthya Karyakram (RBSK) under Ayushman Bharat

While these schemes promote social-emotional learning, they often lack a structured meditative component. SYM can fill this gap, offering a culturally rooted, low-cost, and standardized practice for emotional development across schools.

Strengthening Teacher Participation: The combination of the Research-to-Practice (RTP) model with the Solace for Ruffled Minds (SFRM) framework enables: SYM delivery led by in-house teachers, Local adaptation and implementation without relying on external experts, Scalable training opportunities through platforms like DIETs or SCERTs

This model fosters decentralization of wellness education and allows it to become an integral part of everyday school life. In conclusion, SYM presents a policy-aligned, research-supported, and scalable solution that bridges the current disconnect between educational objectives and students’ emotional well-being, making it a valuable addition to India’s school systems.

Limitations: Although the outcomes of this study are encouraging, it is essential to consider certain limitations to properly contextualize the findings and inform future research directions.

a. Limited Sample Size and Urban Focus: The study focused on three secondary schools in Navi Mumbai, offering a limited urban sample. Therefore, applying these findings to rural schools, different educational boards, or diverse communities is uncertain without further study. The SYM intervention lasted eight weeks, which was enough for initial results but may not show lasting psychological and behavioral changes that need longer engagement. Despite using random assignment in schools, the overall study was quasi-experimental, not a double-blind RCT, allowing for possible selection bias or contextual effects on outcomes.

b. **Dependence on Self-Reported Data:** The primary quantitative data was gathered through self-assessment tools, which present several challenges:

- Responses may have been influenced by a desire to present oneself favorably (social desirability bias)
- Younger students may have misunderstood certain scale items
- Emotional experiences could have been exaggerated or understated

To strengthen future research, it is advisable to incorporate objective metrics such as physiological data (e.g., heart rate variability) or performance-based indicators (e.g., academic records, attendance).

- **Facilitator Expertise Variability:** Although SYM sessions followed a consistent format, the facilitators had different levels of qualifications and experience. Some sessions were led by school teachers, while others were conducted by external volunteers with varying expertise. These differences in delivery may have affected the results of the intervention. While these limitations are important to note, they point to areas where the research design can be improved, especially when expanding the program to larger groups.
- **Recommendations and Future Scope:** This study provides a foundation for including Sahaja Yoga Meditation in India's secondary schools. Based on the findings and challenges, suggestions are made for progress at the institutional, policy, technology, and research levels.
- **Institutional Recommendations:** Schools should include SYM sessions in daily routines, such as during assemblies or value education classes, with 10-15 minutes of practice each day. Workshops should be held to train teachers to lead SYM sessions effectively. Additionally, B.Ed. and D.Ed. programs should incorporate SYM facilitation training.

Policy level recommendation: SYM should be formally integrated into NCERT's mental health resources, the CBSE Life Skills curriculum, and NEP 2020's value-based learning modules. State or district-level pilot programs in government schools, particularly in high-pressure areas, are recommended to assess and improve SYM's effectiveness in diverse public contexts.

- **Technological Support:** Develop a mobile app and video series for schools without SYM facilitators. A SYM Schools Portal could provide training materials and track student progress.

- **Future Research:** Studies should examine how regular SYM practice affects academic performance and life satisfaction during transition to adulthood. Include diverse student populations, using EEG, GSR, and HRV to validate benefits.
- **Family Involvement:** Extend SYM to parents and families to enhance meditation benefits and build emotional resilience. These recommendations could help stakeholders maximize SYM as a cost-effective tool for empowering India's youth.

Conclusion: This research presents a well-rounded, evidence-driven approach to tackling mental health concerns among adolescents in Indian secondary schools through the application of Sahaja Yoga Meditation (SYM). By employing a mixed-methods approach and integrating insights from three core frameworks—SYM-focused empirical studies, Indian Knowledge Systems (IKS), and the Solace for Ruffled Minds (SFRM) implementation guide—this research illustrates how SYM can be implemented as a secular, affordable, and scalable solution. Quantitative results demonstrated notable improvements in emotional maturity and significant decreases in stress, aggression, and social anxiety. Alongside this, qualitative feedback indicated that students experienced enhanced calmness, greater self-awareness, and emotional stability—observations supported by both teachers and student journals. Collectively, these results confirm SYM's potential to improve emotional regulation, academic focus, and overall mental well-being. Additionally, the proposed Research-to-Practice (RTP) framework is not only a theoretical model but also a practical roadmap for school administrators, mental health experts, and policymakers aiming to integrate SYM into formal education systems. As India works towards creating a progressive educational ecosystem centred on mental health and well-being, SYM emerges as a culturally apt, no-cost, and research-supported strategy to meet the increasing emotional needs of its youth. The responsibility now falls on educators, policymakers, and researchers to advance this initiative, widen its scope, enhance its implementation, and adapt it for future generations.

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